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MEMCAT

Membrane-assisted Ethylene Synthesis over Nanostructured Tandem Catalysts

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Start date of project: 01/05/2024

Duration: 4 years

D5.2 Plan for Dissemination, including Communication Activities

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1. Introduction

This document serves as the initial version of the dissemination and communication plan for the MemCat project. It outlines a comprehensive master plan for all dissemination and communication activities to be carried out throughout the project, detailing all potential actions and initiatives. The plan establishes clear objectives for communication and dissemination, along with specifying target audiences and appropriate channels. This deliverable contributes to the task 5.2 “Dissemination of the Dissemination plan” of the Work Package 5 “Dissemination and Exploitation”. The task is led by 1CUBE and sees the contribution of all partners.

The communication channels and objectives have been carefully selected to address the diverse target audiences of the MemCat project. These audiences include public and private institutions, policy makers, other Horizon Europe projects, the scientific community, industrial partners and companies, investors, and the broader society.

This document outlines the strategy and specific actions necessary for effective dissemination and communication of the project's results, as part of Work Package 5 (WP5). The development and continuous updating of the Dissemination and Communication Plan form the foundation for maximizing the impact of the MemCat project and its outcomes.

The activities detailed in this deliverable are designed to inform, engage, raise awareness, and promote information about the project, including its objectives, funding source, and results. To achieve this, it is crucial to establish and maintain effective communication channels, identify key stakeholders, and deliver information in the most suitable manner.

These activities will be carried out throughout the entire 48-month duration of the project.

The plan will be periodically revised throughout the project to fine-tune the dissemination and communication objectives in alignment with emerging project results. The current plan aims to address the following key points:

- I. Define target groups and identify key stakeholders;
- II. Establish clear communication objectives and the strategies to achieve them;
- III. Develop and maintain a list of targeted events, scientific conferences, and trade fairs (this list is updated on the Teams of the project and in the project website);
- IV. Compile a list of dissemination and communication activities.

For each MemCat partner, this Master Plan will serve as the foundation for their outreach and dissemination activities, specifically to:

- I. Inform the public and target audiences about communication actions;
- II. Guide project partners in planning their individual communication activities;
- III. Define related management, monitoring, and reporting activities;
- IV. Provide guidance for media and public relations activities involving the MemCat consortium.

2. Description of actions

Dissemination and communication activities are crucial to the success of the MemCat project. While dissemination focuses on engaging specific target audiences through tailored channels, communication aims to reach the general public. To ensure effectiveness in both areas, a well-defined strategy is essential, beginning with the identification of target groups.

2.1 Target Groups and Stakeholders

An analysis of relevant stakeholders for the MemCat solutions is essential to identify target groups and assess the positions of various stakeholders regarding the project's results. This analysis will inform engagement strategies and help establish connections and synergies with ongoing EU projects for mutual benefit. While stakeholder analysis is an ongoing process, an initial list of target groups was identified during the proposal writing phase, refined over recent months, and is presented below:

- Scientific community
 - ✓Fellow researchers, PhD students, School graduates, Students & professionals
- RDI community (including all the following targets)
 - ✓Hydrogen RDI community
 - ✓Catalysis, CO₂ capture and conversion RDI community
 - ✓Membrane and gas separation RDI community
 - ✓Process technology RDI community
 - ✓RDI project consortia related to MemCat technologies
- Plant community
 - ✓Plant owners and Operators
 - ✓European Ethylene Producers Committee ([EEPC](#))
 - ✓European plant building & equipment
- Research admin. and funding authorities
- Associations related to MemCat technologies (e.g., renewable energy, chemical industry, and catalysis)
- Policy makers
- Investors
- Banks
- General public

The MemCat partners will be asked to further define and refine the list of Target groups. The contact list being developed will serve as a dissemination tool and later on as a forum for potential future cooperation.

Target groups that can be directly involved in the project activities at different levels were initially identified. Mapping and fine-tuning of the list will be performed continuously to also fine-tune the communication activities. After identification of the target groups, within the communication plan, particular actions are determined to follow the appropriate communication paths to each target.

2.2 Dissemination activities

Dissemination activities will be designed to create awareness of the MemCat results to the different target groups. Some dissemination activities will serve different target groups, while others are designed for specific ones. MemCat has also targets in terms of dissemination activities. The dissemination activities designed at M6 are reported in the table below.

Level	Targeted audience	Activities to achieve the objective	Targeted number	Performance indicator
Awareness of the MemCat results	Scientific community: scientists in the relevant research field	Publications (e.g., Nature and other Nature Research journals, Science, JACS, Angew. Chem. Int. Ed., ACS Catal., Chem. Eng. J.), conference attendances (e.g., ICC, EuropaCat, NAM, Carbon Dioxide Conversion Catalysis Conference, Carbon Dioxide Utilisation Summit, ICCMR, ICIM), website, social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube), and organization of scientific workshop	5 publications/year; 5 conference attendances/year, 4 monthly posts on social media, scientific workshop at M18	Citations, visits to website, reactions on social media, number of people attending the conference highlights about MemCat outputs
Awareness of the MemCat results and the industry community	Relevant industry: chemical industry, CO ₂ -intensive industries, industrial players in green H ₂	Conference organization, Hackathon co-creation event, direct contacts through partners' own network, website, social media, press releases, contacts established through the advisory board	Exploitation workshop at M36, 4 monthly posts on social media, 3 press releases	N° of people attending the events, n° of contacts made, visits to website, reactions on social media
Awareness creation for public authorities & and major EU stakeholders	Business and support networks: renewable energy, chemical industry, catalysis associations Policy makers: governmental organizations, regulatory authorities	Memberships of committees and boards, meetings with public authorities, memberships in associations, e.g., CO ₂ Value Europe, European Materials Modelling Council, Hydrogen Europe Research, CCUS Projects Network, Petrochemicals Europe, Plastics Europe; participation to events organized by EU/national/regional authorities	5 attendances to meetings of associations/year, 5 participations to events/year	Num. of presentations of MemCat in association meetings and external events

2.3 Communication activities

As for the dissemination activities, also communication activities are designed for different Target audiences. The Tools used for dissemination are reported in the table below, while examples of tools used so far are reported in the next sections.

Target audience/Main message	Tools and channels/Details
<p>General EU public and wider scientific community: to create awareness of MemCat activities, results, and importance of moving towards sustainable production of commodity chemicals</p>	<p>MemCat website: The website will contain information on the project goals and achievements, importance of sustainability in the production of chemicals and avoiding the use of fossil-based sources as raw materials. The website will also feature news, project events, outputs, and conference attendances. Number of visits will be monitored by INL.</p>
	<p>Twitter, LinkedIn: Social media channels of the project and the channels of the participating institutions will be used to highlight project relevance and results, publications, conferences, and relevant developments in the field. YouTube: Short informative videos will be prepared about the project partners, project goals, results, etc. The social media content will target to include 50% featuring women. Impact will be monitored by 1Cube.</p>
	<p>TV, newspapers: Press releases on MemCat results of interest for the general public will be prepared and sent to the national media. Media coverage will be monitored by 1Cube.</p>
	<p>Hackathon co-creation event: A challenge-driven co-creation event, in collaboration with the industry by engaging for example with the companies invited to the exploitation workshop at M36. To co-create and anticipate future sustainable technologies and increase the public acceptance thereof, promoting a quicker acceptance by the general public to the market.</p>
<p>Young people, School students: to increase interest in science as career, highlight importance of sustainability</p>	<p>Outreach: Events (EU Researchers' Night, International Day of Women and Girls in Science, local Open Day activities) will be utilized raise interest in science and to underline the importance of sustainability in chemical production. All MemCat partners have experience in presenting at such events. Each partner will take part in at least one such activity/year. These events will be advertised on social media and featured in posts. School visits: Each partner will conduct visits to local schools and institutes to expose students to the importance of science and sustainability in chemical production. MemCat partners have experience in such visits. Each partner will take part in at least one such activity. Presenting scientists will be selected to highlight gender equality and visibility for women in science. Impact will be monitored by the presenting partner.</p>

3. Update first months of the Dissemination and Communication activities

The Dissemination and Communication activities started already at first month of the project with the creation and realization of the website, detailed in the deliverable D5.1 “*Website and project logo information with also social media links*”, and with all social media.

The MemCat website is always updated with the last news and dissemination activities: <https://www.memcatproject.eu/news/>

In addition to Instagram, Youtube Channel, LinkedIn and Facebook, 1Cube opened an X account where all the activities of MemCat are going to be shared.

Figure 1. Screenshot X account

3.1 Dissemination Activities from the Partners

The table below is intended to report and keep track of all the dissemination initiatives at the partners’ level to be updated each six months. 1Cube will request a monthly update from partners to keep this list updated and to share the info through the website and other dissemination channels.

Type of activities n.1	Researchers’ Night
Main leader	UNICAL
Title	MemCat project
Date	27 September 2024
Place	University of Calabria, Italy
Type of Audience	Scientific
Estimate Num. of person reached	200
Countries addressed	Italy

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Type of activities n.2	Netherlands Process technology Symposium (NPS 19)
Main leader	1Cube
Title	MemCat project
Date	8-9 October 2024
Place	Groningen, NL
Type of Audience	Scientific
Estimate Num. of person reached	220
Countries addressed	EU, UK, Asia

3.2 Printed materials

All the printed materials have been shared in social media and can also be downloaded from the MemCat website: <https://www.memcatproject.eu/dissemination/>

- Brochures

- Flyers

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3.3 First Newsletter of MemCat Project

Newsletters and also papers, articles, publications, presentation and poster can also be downloaded from the MemCat website:

<https://www.memcatproject.eu/newsletters/>

MEMCAT NEWSLETTER

Ed. 1 - September, 2024

"Membrane-assisted ethylene synthesis over nanostructured tandem catalysts"

CALL: HORIZON-EIC-2023-PATHFINDEROPEN-01
 PROJECT NUMBER: 101130047
 EU FUNDING: € 3.867 841,25
 STARTING DATE: 01.05.2024
 DURATION: 48 MONTHS

A talk with the Coordinator about the Project

- Hello Mr. Yury V. Kolen'ko, You are the Coordinator of MemCat project, could you tell us more about yourself and your work?

Hi, nice to meet you!
 My name is Yury and I'm a research group leader at the International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory (INL) located in Braga, Portugal.

My group focuses on the synthesis and investigation of unconventional nanomaterials, with a particular emphasis on structure-property relationships in nanoparticles, nanocrystals, and nanostructures.

- Sounds Interesting! What type of project is it? And why is it called MemCat?

MemCat is a collaborative EIC Pathfinder Open project funded by the Horizon Europe.

The Consortium involves various partners, including universities, research organizations, and a SME. The name MemCat stems from the fact that the goal of the project is the development of a catalytic membrane reactor for the conversion of CO₂ to ethylene.

www.memcatproject.eu

3.4. Dissemination and Communication Follow up

In the following months, 1Cube is going to create a first video presenting MemCat objectives, concept and expected results. Different posters and a roll up will be created by 1CUBE in coordination with the partners to advertise MemCat in different events.

The material will be custom made per event, while some general materials will also be created and printed. They can be used in every dissemination event. Also, the partners of the MemCat project will contribute to the Dissemination of the project, participating in different events such as conference, symposium, meetings (physical and/or online). A dissemination workshop will be held by 1CUBE with all partners to update the dissemination and communication actions.

Moreover, 1Cube will write Newsletters about the progress of the activities and achievements, news updates, events, etc., and dedicated press releases to a network of journalists in Europe who are active in methanol, bioenergy, catalysts, membranes, membrane reactors.

Finally, MemCat will continue to attend to open days, and give lectures at schools and other public events.

4. Conclusions

This first version of the communication plan helps defining the target groups, the communication contents and the implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy.

The aim is two-fold: to create awareness about the project and its results, as well as to engage with the project stakeholders.

The communication activities already started from day one of the project and will continue till M48.

This plan will also be updated regularly to include additional channels or target groups identified by the consortium.